

More on the Christmas cake orb-web spider *Isoxya yatesi* Emerit, 1973 (Araneae: Araneidae) in South Africa

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ABSTRACT: *Isoxya yatesi* Emerit, 1973 is a small orb-weaving spider endemic to South Africa, notable for its hardened, spiny abdomen and its placement within the Afrotropical genus *Isoxya* Simon, 1885. The general morphology, lifestyle, conservation status and distribution of the species in South Africa are discussed, along with images of live specimens.

Keywords: biodiversity, KwaZulu-Natal, Eswatini, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), many Araneidae genera were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), including several species of *Isoxya* Simon, 1885. The genus is represented by 17 species known from Africa and Madagascar and six from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). One of the South African species *Isoxya yatesi* Emerit, 1973 is a small orb-weaving spider, notable for its hardened, brightly decorated abdomen. The species name *yatesi* is dedicated to J.H. Yates, who collected the first specimens. This species is known only from the female (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

The aim of this paper is to present additional information on *I. yatesi* in South Africa with notes of its morphology, lifestyle, distribution and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Isoxya yatesi Emerit, 1973

Isoxya yatesi Emerit, 1973: 683, f. 4 (f); Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 34 (f).

Diagnostic characteristics: Female (Figs 1–5): Carapace dark brown, square with thickened rim around lateral borders with dense layer of short white setae (Fig. 2); integument with small granules bearing short curved white setae; chelicerae dark. Sternum a pale yellow (Fig. 4). Abdomen square wider than long with the anterior and posterior edge of the scutum almost straight when seen from above; four distinct orange-russet conical spines roughly equal in size; shiny yellow-orange in the live specimen; scutum with many sigillae, nearly oval and fairly uniform in size, except for the smaller posterior row; rest of abdomen speckled with orange and black granules, with faint cross like white granules (Fig. 2); abdomen with two similar spines on posterior edge. The abdomen is globular when seen from the side (Fig. 5). Legs are the same colour as the carapace, with the distal parts of the longer segments black bearing purplish metallic reflections. Male unknown.

Figures 1–2. *Isoxya yatesi* female. 1. Line drawing of dorsal view. 2. Female from Kloof. Credits: 1. After Emerit (1973). 2. Andrea Sander.

Figures 3–5. *Isoxya yatesi* female from Atherstone Nature Reserve. 3. Dorsal view. 4. Ventral view. 5. Lateral view. Credit: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Variation: *Isoxya* species are known for their brightly coloured, sclerotised abdomens with spines, often featuring yellow, red, or white markings. From Eswatini, a dark specimen was photographed showing the body and legs black with only the cross-like white granules on the abdomen and the tip of the spines with a reddish shine (Fig. 6). Melanism has hitherto not been formally documented in *Isoxya* species.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Eswatini (new record based on iNaturalist observation).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Isoxya yatesi* is a rare spider and is currently known only from four localities in South Africa: two in Limpopo and two in KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 7). It was sampled from the Savanna biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 6. *Isoxya yatesi* female from Maphiveni, Eswatini (iNaturalist). Credit: Ed Millard.

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LIFESTYLE

It is an orb-web spider that Yates (1968) sampled from Pinetown, KwaZulu-Natal. The spider was found on a small geometric web made between two clumps of grass.

CONSERVATION MEASURES

It is known only from the female and is currently listed as Data Deficient. Therefore further sampling is needed to identify the male and determine the species' range. The species receives some protection in the Atherstone Nature Reserve and Wolkberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

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